

Use of Human Genotoxicity Methods to Assess the Radiosensitivity of Cancer Patients

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A variety of different methods have been used to investigate the radiosensitivity of cancer patients treated with radiotherapy in order to predict the risk for developing adverse effects, improve the therapeutic success, and patient's quality-of-life. The most investigations were realised with peripheral blood cells from head and neck cancer, breast cancer, and prostate cancer patients. The irradiation response of patient-derived lymphocytes has been associated with acute and late normal tissue reactions to radiotherapy. The approaches which were used include measurements of cytotoxic effects (including apoptosis and cell cycle delay), identification and analyses of specific genes and use of methods which reflect genotoxicity and DNA repair. The most frequently employed approaches that detect damage of the genotoxic material which is induced by ionizing radiation (double strand breaks and oxidative damage) are chromosomal aberration (CA) analyses of metaphase cells, micronucleus (MN) experiments detecting structural and numerical CA, γ H2AX assays which can be used to measure double strand breaks, and single cell gel electrophoresis (SCGE) assays reflecting single and double DNA strand breaks. Individual differences in the repair capacity were mainly studied in SCGE experiments in which the time kinetics of the disappearance of “comets” was measured. Overall the results of these studies are highly controversial, possibly due to inconsistent experimental designs and methodological shortcomings (including small study groups). However, the possible correlations between repair kinetics of radiation-induced DNA damage in cancer patient lymphocytes after irradiation and the severity of radiotherapy adverse effects should be further explored in larger cohorts. In the last years standardised/validated protocols have been pushed for MN, SCGE, γ H2AX, and DNA repair (BER and NER) experiments with humans that will be used in an ongoing Horizon Europe Twinning project (RadExIORSBoost 101158832) to identify biological parameters which reflect the individual normal tissue radiosensitivity of patients with prostate cancer undergoing radiotherapy.

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